

Literature Review of Music Artificial Intelligence in Education: China and Foreign

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 11, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Music, Artificial Intelligence, Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7424700</p>	<p><i>The research of artificial intelligence since the last century, has nearly a century of history, but the real experimental research results and literature research results are relatively scarce in China, but foreign literature research in recent years, which can be seen in recent years, artificial intelligence as an international hot topic, has fascinated the academic researchers, even in a day have nearly 10 articles published; and the domestic artificial intelligence research is still only the possibility of a predictable impact on human life. This paper expounds on the domestic and foreign research results and summarizes the research results of the music artificial intelligence project at home and abroad.</i></p>

Introduction

In recent a decade, the domestic study of music artificial intelligence is relatively scarce, music spread in China the history is short, artificial intelligence is only in the 20th century after the emerging field, history is short, used in the music industry technology is not mature, make music artificial intelligence become a novel field, research content blank part more. At present, CNKI and several major literature databases show that the study of music artificial intelligence in China is mainly journal articles, with few master's and doctoral papers.

Literature review of music AI research in China

As of November 8, 2021, we have conducted an advanced search with the keyword "music artificial intelligence" on CNKI, with a total of 5 excellent papers. Searching with the keyword "music artificial intelligence" from the Wanfang database, there were 107 dissertations and 326 journal papers. It is mainly summarized in the following pieces:

First, the emergence of artificial intelligence, but also produced a series of judicial problems. The protection of intellectual property rights and copyright of music works has become a hot topic in the intellectual property system of the legal circle. Some authors believe that the right ownership of musical works created by AI should belong to the two types of AI composition developers and users, and some authors also believe that the copyright should belong to human beings themselves.

Second, the reform and change of online music education have improved the characteristics of traditional music education that cannot give full play to their subjective initiative in students, improved the efficiency of music teaching, and cultivated students' interest in music and the spirit of inquiry. Spontaneous online music education in schools or social online music education can help to promote the fairness of music education resources, to promote the promotion and innovative development of music education resources.

Third, the cultivation of music artificial intelligence talents is closely related to industry development. For example, in 2019, the Central Conservatory of Music began to recruit doctoral students in music artificial intelligence and music information technology. The doctoral students in this direction will be trained by dual tutors (music education tutor + technology enterprise supervisor), and the length of schooling is three years. This is a combination of the artificial intelligence discipline and the music discipline. It can be seen that the development trend of music artificial intelligence is looking good,

Fourth, another part of the research content is: in the use of music streaming media, the big data analysis under artificial intelligence is used to "classify and summarize" all online users, and then a series of algorithms are used to guess the users' "thoughts".

Fifth, the last part, from the point of view of communication, the core function of music communicators, the value of the content of music transmission, the transformation of the music media development, music user experience, and the risk of music transmission are artificial intelligence, the influence of legal ethical problems are also taken out for the study and analysis.

Literature review of international music AI research

International research on music AI is more and more systematic. Searching SpringerLink with the keyword "Music AI", there were nearly 5,000 results from 2020 to 2022 alone, including manual books, master's papers, journals, and other documents, and related subjects including computer science, engineering, business management, sociology, and other disciplines. Here I have summarized some of the literature related to my research content and summarized them:

Research began to turn to the creativity of sound and music interacting with computers, from sound interaction design with physical objects, the development, and evaluation of new digital instruments and their expressive capabilities, to the fundamental and exploratory study of sound perception and sound experience semantics, where volume emphasizes the importance of sound in interaction.

The application status of ARTIFICIAL intelligence technology in creative industries introduces the background of artificial intelligence, especially machine learning (ML) algorithms, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), generative adversarial networks (gan), recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and deep reinforcement learning (DRL) and other algorithm technologies. The model constructed by using this kind of algorithm can already meet the basic requirements of composition and performance. Of course, in addition, we should continue and develop, further research music artificial intelligence.

Ethical issues arising from the use of artificial intelligence. Some authors argue that the ethical dilemmas involved in human-computer interaction in the services supported by robotics and artificial intelligence are both numerous and significant. A widespread ethical concern is that we now compare ourselves to machines rather than animals and, therefore, our superiority is fading. Although some of the moral dilemmas presented here are futuristic and speculative, it is time to think about them and take legal, social, and procedural actions to help resolve them.

Facing rapidly developing technology and the Internet, online music courses are complementary to face-to-face learning and higher education. Both college and distance education master programs are available worldwide and offer online opportunities to pursue career development in many universities. Individual online courses are an alternative to music education with live communication. Distance music education courses based on deep learning and data mining in previous methods. Existing methods bring technical challenges, over-filtering, and deployment challenges. This method is based on machine learning for FPGA (Field Programmable gate array) and distance music education courses. Wireless sensors show that adults have various ways to participate in online music training. Therefore, the nature of online communication and teacher-student interaction is different. Have a request. For practice-based or performance-based courses, practical problems such as low-quality audio and time delays may arise. Online learning offers flexibility and internationalization and has a strong ability to connect with many people. In this case, the wireless sensors convey to our teachers from a practical perspective, such as the convenience of transportation and payment. Further educational efforts will also need to promote music and online distance education.

Theoretical basis

In many contemporary societies, the increasing spread of technology, from communications to social networks, digital health and welfare services, and every aspect of social life in industrialized societies is targeted at technological upgrading, optimized services, or automatic pairing management. Among these technologies, machine learning (Machine Learning) and the wider field of AI have received considerable attention over the past few decades. Research over the past decade shows that data-driven learning-based algorithms can be implemented in many tasks that were not yet imagined. Since the breakthrough of deep learning that began in 2012, these algorithms have been shown to recognize images just like humans, gain motor control from very few observations, and then understand and respond to several human languages. These breakthroughs have prompted significant investments in the sector, thus accelerating the exponential pace of technological advances in the sector. By interacting with these technologies, people produce large amounts of usage data, which, in turn, are used to train the underlying algorithm. Thus, the technology type is divorced from people's control and understanding. Artists have always been one of the first people to question technological innovation. Our approach changes the use and reflection on AI as an actor in a performance, a functional entity that can be used to question the understanding of computational intelligence in Western societies.

The music creation is divided into two parts: music composition and music arrangement. These two parts are the most important and innovative steps in music creation. At present, some foreign companies have produced composition and arrangement models. Of course, in addition to some models and tools proposed by individuals, there are also some models and tools for music generation published by companies or individuals on the Internet. The generation and refinement of these model tools make it possible for artificial intelligence composition to replace human artists.

The process of music mixing is only the most important creation stage after music creation, so it is called "secondary creation" by musicians. This is the process of putting a series of different pieces of music together while applying a series of audio processing to mix the tracks in a pleasing aesthetic way. Music mixing

exercises require a tool for various aspects of a musical work using a delightful combination of engineering techniques to do so. Music mixing needs to consider the five key ingredients to a mix, they are balance, spectrum, space, depth, and dynamics (dynamic). (Owsinski, 2013) The combination of these five aspects is usually done through a series of different audio effects. Depending on preference, perceived quality, and emotional perception, the way a piece of music is mixed can greatly affect the way it is perceived. Music mixing is a highly complex, multi-dimensional process problem that many different complex sounds are combined in many different ways. Processing and modification of each track rely on musical mixing within all other tracks, often requiring different processing and effects in different parts of the song. For example, the application of some equalizer settings in the chorus may be very different from the balancer settings required in the poem. This result, in a highly complex nonlinear search space, heavily depends on human perceived preference for music and human auditory and emotional limitations in response to music.

Since the 1980s, computer software has been able to send messages to acoustic pianos, allowing for the development of automatic combination performances of playing piano music on pianos (De Poli, 2004). As the algorithm generated improved classical/romantic standards (mainly piano) new research questions appeared: whether when an audience can't distinguish an algorithm performing work rather than a professional human performer of recording algorithm ability or from then on, the robot becomes like a human has been very attractive automation and robotics the possibility of robotics music (Kapur, 2005). A famous example is the computer "can beat a world chess champion, and the computer" Deep Blue " was able to reach this milestone by defeating his opponent. After years of defeat, world champion Gary Kasparov won the official tournament in 1997. A few decades later, when the robot performs on stage, the audience can't tell a professional human performance from an algorithm, unless the algorithm adds no expressive nuances, that is unless it performs the notes in a popular, expressionless, mechanical way. And expert classical music piano players, who will have some professional music knowledge and musical style, can reproduce human performance without distinguishing between expressive algorithms. So, a human pianist can imitate humans very well. This conclusion leads people to propose an important argument about artificial intelligence, whether artificial intelligence can replace human art. Like Deep Blue computers beating human player chess in matches, the current algorithms may make people redundant.

Definition of important concepts

The definition of AI: The concept of early AI was proposed by Marvin Minsky (Marvin Minsky), the father of artificial intelligence, who believed that AI is a science about making machines competent for tasks that require human intelligence to accomplish. While the core of this definition remains true today, modern computer scientists have further defined AI as a system that senses the environment and takes action to maximize the amount of success in achieving its goals. Not only that, AI systems can interpret and analyze data and can learn and adjust in the process.

In SAP, AI is defined as a system with the ability to interpret and analyze data and perceive the environment and take actions to maximize achievement. The three types of artificial intelligence are the narrow sense of artificial intelligence (ANI), general artificial intelligence (AGI), and super artificial intelligence (ASI).

The core technology of AI: The first is machine learning (machine learning and all of its components are subsets of AI. Machine learning applies various algorithms to different types of learning methods and analysis techniques, allowing the system to automatically learn from experience and improve constantly, without explicit programming. There is a difference between AI and machine learning. Machine learning is a part of artificial intelligence. Without AI, there is no machine learning, so they don't have to be different from each other, but how they are different. AI is based on data processing to make decisions and predictions. With machine learning algorithms, artificial intelligence can not only process data but also learn without any additional programming; the second is natural language processing (NLP), with NLP technology to recognize and understand written language and speech commands, including translating human language into language that algorithms can understand; the third is computer vision, which helps computers view and understands digital images and videos, not just identifies or classify them. The fourth is robotics. Above definition of SAP view, the current human definition of artificial intelligence is not enough to complete, because the goal of artificial intelligence can be achieved as scientific and technological achievements, and not fully defined, in this paper, the definition of artificial intelligence is mainly mentioned above the core technology of artificial intelligence (machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, and robotics) is analyzed.

Music artificial intelligence (Music Artificial Intelligence, MAI): In recent years, this word has been produced in many fields, such as music and computers. This is a relatively popular concept, but it has a certain ambiguity, which can be understood so that, that is, artificial intelligence has been applied vertically in the category of music, namely music generation, etc., and also includes all the applications related to AI and music, such as intelligent music education and analysis, etc. Music AI should be divided into one aspect of music technology.

Pop music (popular music) can also be known as commercial music, also known as pop songs, modern pop music, specifically refers to a period for the public to accept the love and popular popularity of music can be defined as pop music. Pop music originated in the United States at the end of the 19th century and the early 20th century. From the perspective of the music system, pop music was developed based on American pop music architecture such as Dingding Lane songs, blues, jazz, and rock music. Its styles are diversified and rich, such as Jazz, Rock, Soul, Blue, Reggae, RP, HP-Hop, Disco, New Age, Funk, R & B, and other modern pop music born after the 20th century.

Music composition (Composition) is the most important and innovative step in music creation, and some foreign companies have produced composition models. At present, there have been some music generation models and tools published by companies or individuals on the Internet. The generation and improvement of these model tools make it possible for artificial intelligence composition to replace human artists.

Music blending (Music Mixing) refers to the process of making music, placing a variety of sound sources in a stereo or single, or even surround track, which may come from different instruments, vocals, or orchestral music. However, the music mixing techniques and methods of the past were very different from the present, with the devices usually used to mix music, such as synthesizers, sound processors, and mixing stations. Nowadays, with the development of technology, only computers and mixing software can be needed to complete the complicated mixing operations done before.

Music performance (Music Performance) needs to generate performances on stage, and for artificial intelligence, generating human music expression is one of the most challenging aspects of computer music that has only recently been addressed. The main problem of modeling expression is to master the "touch point" of the performer, that is, the knowledge used when performing the score. Humans acquire it through long-term observation and imitation. Therefore, previous approaches used to try to capture explanatory knowledge based on following the rules of music have serious limitations. Another approach closer to the human observation-imitation process is to directly use the explanatory knowledge implicit in the examples extracted from the recordings of human performers, rather than attempting to clarify this knowledge.

Conclusion

With the advent of the new era, won the rapid development of science and technology, makes a lot of composers create music and technology together, to make music and sound concept for more clear presentation, which promotes the composer and science and technology experts have a closer collaboration between them, common effort, to music works.

Since the 1980s, computer software has been able to send messages to acoustic pianos, allowing for the development of automatic combination performances of playing piano music on pianos (De Poli, 20 04). As the algorithm generated improved classical/romantic standards (mainly piano) new research questions appeared: whether when an audience can't distinguish an algorithm performing work rather than a professional human performer of recording algorithm ability or from then on, the robot becomes like a human has been very attractive automation and robotics the possibility of robotics music (Kapur, 2005). A famous example is the computer "can beat a world chess champion, and the computer" Deep Blue " was able to reach this milestone by defeating his opponent. After years of defeat, world champion Gary Kasparov won the official tournament in 1997. A few decades later, when the robot performs on stage, the audience can't tell a professional human performance from an algorithm, unless the algorithm adds no expressive nuances, that is unless it performs the notes in a popular, expressionless, mechanical way. And expert classical music piano players, who will have some professional music knowledge and musical style, can reproduce human performance without distinguishing between expressive algorithms. So, a human pianist can imitate humans very well. This conclusion leads people to propose an important argument about artificial intelligence, whether artificial intelligence can replace human art. Like Deep Blue computers beating human player chess in matches, the current algorithms may make people redundant.

In the past decade, emerging electronic music is also the result of the combination of artificial intelligence technology development and music." Electronic music" is to make music through a series of technical means to produce different sound effects, and these kinds of sound effects are used in music is also deeply popular with the public, it is the typical case of this development process. Computers involved in music creation, some people regard it as a mechanized participation, in present, the computer in it, as an interactive object, that also faces a lot of technical problems, so, at the moment, such "interactive" electronic music, has not been a lot of recognition and widespread use, did not become the main direction of music life. However, many composers and scientific and technical experts with advanced ideas are very concerned about this, and under their promotion, this aspect is undergoing extremely significant changes. It is believed that in the future, with the further advancement of The Times, there will be more and better works to be constructed, and this new type of music will also be widely valued by people.

Music artificial intelligence has brought a lot of convenience to all the processes of music production, reducing the work pressure on musicians to a certain extent, but it is also constantly eroding people's creativity

and innovation ability. Whether artificial intelligence will completely replace music mixing and mixing artists, and how to keep human artists alive and keep them creative, is a point worth studying deeply.

This study will combine the produced models of the past and the actual output, and combine with the practical theory, what are the changes in the thinking of contemporary human artists in the three steps of pop music production? What is the theoretical direction? What are the effects on human artists?

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